

The Prospects and Challenges of Shale Oil Exploration in Nigeria

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Abstract

Nigeria is one of the largest producers of oil and gas in Africa, 10th in the world and possesses vast reserves; but with continuous increase in population and demand for petroleum and petroleum products, the conventional hydrocarbon reserves are being rapidly utilized, it is feared that the demand for conventional oil will exceed supply in the nearest future. Nigeria is also a major exporter of the conventional oil and its products to the United States of America, but with the recent discovery, demand and relevance of shale oil in the world market especially by the U.S government, there has been a decline in the demand cum prize of crude oil, which has affected Nigeria since her income and revenue largely depends on it. Nigeria has vast reserves of shale oil deposits in Benue, Abakaliki, Borno, Adamawa, Imo, Abia, Calabar, and other south-east and north-eastern parts of the country. Hence, this review includes the formation of petroleum, shale oil, characteristics, global shale oil exploration, comparison of petroleum and shale oil, and the prospects and challenges of shale oil exploration. In conclusion, Nigeria should be encouraged to invest in the relatively neglected shale oil as a potential alternative source of energy, thereby increasing the nation's oil reserves and diversifying of energy sources.

Keywords: Prospects, Challenges, Shale oil and Exploration.

Introduction

The global population continues to grow, leading to a corresponding rise in energy demand. Concerns have been raised over the depletion of crude oil, currently the primary energy source, prompting the exploration of alternative energy options such as shale oil. As a result, the shift from conventional to unconventional hydrocarbon exploration has become an inevitable trend in the petroleum industry (Zhou et al., 2018). Global petroleum demand is projected to rise steadily over the next 25 years, increasing from approximately 80 million barrels per day to nearly 120 million barrels per day by 2025 (Biglari et al., 2007). In response, technologically advanced nations such as the United States, Brazil, China, and Estonia have invested significantly in shale oil exploration and are already benefiting from its development (Osuji, 2015).

In contrast, Nigeria's oil and gas sector faces numerous challenges, including rising domestic demand for petroleum products, dwindling conventional reserves, and global oil price volatility (Obasi, 2013). Despite being heavily reliant on crude oil for both energy and national revenue, with oil accounting for approximately 75% of the country's income (Agbaeze et al., 2015), Nigeria has yet to venture into shale oil production. This continued dependence on traditional crude oil underscores the urgent need for diversification within the energy sector.

Nigeria's overreliance on a single commodity—crude oil—and the associated volatility in production levels and fluctuations in international oil prices have raised serious concerns about the sustainability of the country's

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oil and gas sector. As the largest oil and gas producer in Africa and a key exporter of crude oil to the United States, Nigeria holds a significant position in the global energy market. In 2010, Nigeria exported over one million barrels of crude oil per day to the United States, accounting for approximately 9% of U.S. total crude oil and petroleum imports and 40% of Nigeria's exports. This highlights the extent to which Nigeria's economy is vulnerable to external policy shifts and market dynamics. Notably, the global pivot toward shale oil, particularly by the United States, has led to a significant decline in both the demand and price of conventional crude oil, adversely affecting Nigeria's revenue stream, which remains heavily dependent on oil exports (Erude et al., 2023).

In light of this, there is a compelling need for Nigeria—and indeed the global community—to explore alternative energy sources beyond conventional oil. Shale oil represents a viable option for energy diversification. Shales are sedimentary rocks formed from compacted silt and clay, typically rich in organic matter and cementing materials. They contain a variety of minerals, including feldspars, calcite, clay minerals, mica, pyrite, quartz, organic carbon, and iron oxides, distributed within the rock's matrix. Of these, clay and quartz are the predominant components, comprising approximately 57% and 25% of the rock by weight, respectively.

Shale oil refers to liquid hydrocarbons that exist in free, dissolved, or adsorbed states within source rocks such as mudstones or shales. These hydrocarbons remain in the formation after the initial phases of hydrocarbon generation and expulsion (Jiang et al., 2016). Historically, shale oil development has been limited due to the relative ease and lower cost of extracting conventional oil and gas. However, with the progressive depletion of conventional reserves, there is an urgent need to assess and exploit Nigeria's shale oil resources as a means to bolster the nation's energy security and diversify its revenue base.

Accordingly, this review paper examines the concept of petroleum, the geology of shale formations, the characteristics and production of shale oil, and the distinctions between shale oil and conventional crude oil. It also explores the prospects and challenges of shale oil development in Nigeria, with a view to promoting sustainable energy diversification and economic resilience.

Crude Oil (Petroleum)

Crude oil, also known as petroleum, is a naturally occurring liquid found beneath the Earth's surface that can be processed into various fuels. It is a type of fossil fuel formed from the remains of ancient organic materials that were subjected to extreme heat and pressure over millions of years. The composition of crude oil includes both straight and branched chain aliphatic hydrocarbons, ranging from light gases like methane to thick, tar-like substances with as many as 80 carbon atoms (Pandolfo et al., 2023).

In its raw, unrefined state, crude oil is often called “black gold.” It was first discovered in Nigeria in 1956 at Oloibiri, located in Bayelsa State in the Niger Delta region. According to the Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC), Nigeria holds the largest oil and gas reserves in Africa and ranks as the tenth largest crude oil producer globally. The Niger Delta basin yields two main types of crude oil: light and heavy. The lighter variant has an API gravity of about 36, while the heavier ranges between 20 and 25; both types are paraffinic and contain low levels of sulfur (Ofodile et al., 2018).

Petroleum remains the primary energy source in Nigeria. It is essential for powering vehicles, heating systems, and machinery, and is also a raw material in the production of numerous goods and materials (Abas et al., 2015). As the global demand for petroleum and its derivatives continues to rise, the industry has seen significant technological advancements in exploration and extraction. This evolution includes a move from traditional sources to unconventional resources, exemplified by the successful development of shale oil and gas in North America (Zhou et al., 2018).

Formation of Petroleum

The formation of petroleum is divided into three steps namely: diagenesis, catagenesis and metamorphism (genesis) as shown in **Figure 1**.

Step 1: Diagenesis is a process of compaction under mild conditions of temperature and pressure.

Organic aquatic sediments (proteins, lipids, carbohydrates) when deposited, are very saturated with water and rich in minerals. Through chemical reactions, compaction, and microbial action during burial, water is forced out and proteins and carbohydrates break down to form new structures made up of a waxy material known as “kerogen” and a black tar-like substance called bitumen. The bitumen comprises the heaviest components of petroleum, but kerogen undergoes further changes to form hydrocarbons.

Step 2: Catagenesis (or cracking): The process of catagenesis begins as temperature and pressure increases (deeper burial), resulting in the thermal degradation of kerogen to hydrocarbon chains. The process of catagenesis is catalyzed by the minerals that are deposited and persist through the marine diagenesis. The products are determined by the conditions of the catagenesis, and high temperature and pressure leads to more complete “cracking” of the kerogen and progressively lighter and smaller hydrocarbons. Formation of petroleum requires specific conditions; too hot and the product will favour natural gas (small hydrocarbons), and too cold the plankton will remain trapped as kerogen.

Step 3: Metagenesis: This stage involves higher temperature and pressure verging on metamorphism. Methane gas is the only hydrocarbon released at this point, and the petroleum is said to be matured (Tissot & Welte, 1984).

Figure 1: Formation of petroleum (Tissot & Welte, 1984).

Shales

Shales are sedimentary rocks formed from the compaction of fine-grained materials such as silt and clay. These rocks also contain varying amounts of organic matter and cementing agents. Common minerals found in shales include clay minerals, feldspars, calcite, mica, pyrite, quartz, organic carbon, and iron oxides. These minerals are distributed throughout the silt, clay particles, cementing materials, and organic constituents of the rock. By weight, clay and quartz dominate shale composition, accounting for approximately 57% and 25% respectively.

Classification of Shales

Shales can be classified based on several observable characteristics and their depositional environments. The major classification criteria include texture, mineral composition, type of cementing material, organic content, depositional setting, and mechanical strength.

1. Texture-Based Classification

Shales are composed of clay and very fine-grained silt particles, typically smaller than 0.063 mm. Depending on the dominant component, they are classified as:

- **Silty shale** – when silt predominates
- **Clay shale:** When clay predominates collectively, these are referred to as **argillaceous shales** (Makeen et al., 2015). If shale contains significant sand content, it may be termed **sandy shale** or **arenaceous shale**.

2. Cementing Material-Based Classification

The nature of the cementing agent significantly influences the properties and behavior of shales. Based on the dominant cement, shales can be classified as:

- **Ferruginous shale** – cemented with iron oxide
- **Siliceous shale** – cemented with silica
- **Calcareous (or limy) shale** – cemented with calcite or lime

3. Depositional Environment-Based Classification

Shales form in various sedimentary environments, which influence their composition and structure. The three primary depositional settings include:

- **Lacustrine (continental)** – characterized by mixed sediments of sand, clay, silt, precipitates, inorganic carbonates, freshwater invertebrates, and plant debris.
- **Deltaic (transitional)** – made up of orderly sequences of shale, sand, and sandstone, formed through alternating marine transgressions and regressions; these typically contain kaolinite, illite, and montmorillonite clay minerals and are shallow in depth.
- **Marine** – usually deeper environments where fine sediments accumulate under calm water conditions.

4. Organic Matter Content-Based Classification

Shales rich in organic matter are typically classified as:

- **Carbonaceous shale** – primarily composed of plant-derived organic material
 - **Bituminous shale** – rich in bitumen
- Both types usually have organic matter content exceeding 10%. The presence of organic matter gives shale its characteristic gray or black color; black coloration is often due to iron sulfide. These organic-rich shales are key source rocks for petroleum and natural gas, depending on the quantity and quality of kerogen present.

5. Strength-Based Classification

Shale strength is assessed using the **Slake Durability Index (SDI)**, which measures the rock's resistance to wetting and drying cycles. Based on SDI:

- Shales with an index above 80% are considered **rock-like**

- Shales with an index below 80% are considered **soil-like**

Oil Shale: Oil shale is a sedimentary rock that contains the organic matter kerogen, which is capable of yielding an alternative to conventional petroleum.

Shale Oil: Shale oil is the oil extracted from the kerogen contained in the oil shale (or oil bearing sedimentary rock) (Vandenbroucke & Largeau, 2007). There are two types of shale oil, the free oil and the sorption oil. Free oil usually accumulates in the pores and micro-fractures, and is regarded as movable oil of excellent resource quality. While the sorption oil includes the adsorption and absorption oils; the adsorption oil refers to the oil molecules on the surfaces of structured organic matter and clay minerals. The absorption oil is the oil dissolved in solid organic matter. The sorption (also known as non-movable oil) oil is difficult to extract using hydraulic fracturing technology.

Global Oil Shale Deposits and Development: Oil shale (igniting rock) is one of the world's oldest and largest fossil fuel resources found just as the crude oil in many underground deposits around the world. In the United States of America, there are seven major reserves, they are the Wolf camp /Bone Spring, Bakken/Three Forks, Eagle Ford, Wood Ford, Marcellus, Niobrara, and Barnett, which accounts for about 49.3% of total proved crude oil reserves in the USA (USDI, 2021); which shows the important role of shale oil in energy supply. Other countries like China, Russia, Canada and Argentina have also made progress in shale oil exploration. Shale oil deposits are also found in Estonia, Germany, Israel, Russia and Brazil. In Africa, shale oil deposits are found in South Africa, Egypt, Madagascar and Nigeria (Enze et al., 2022).

The oil and gas producing formations in North America are generally located in marine sedimentary environments. In China, the shale reserves are in the lacustrine systems, such as the Jurassic Ziliujing formations in the Sichuan Basin, the Cretaceous Qingshankou formation in the Songliao Basin, The Yanchang formation in the Ordos Basin, and the Shahejie formation in the Bohai Bay Basin (Enze et al., 2022).

In Nigeria, shale oil deposits are found in Calabar, Benue, Abakaliki, Borno, Adamawa and in other south-east and north-eastern parts of the country (Ogidi et al., 2021; Aniete et al., 2017).

The Prospects of Shale Oil Exploration in Nigeria

Researchers have shown that the Eze-Aku shale in the Abakaliki fold belt and the Ekenkpon shale in Calabar Flank are originally rich, thermally matured, with a total organic carbon (TOC) value of 10 wt.% They have great potential for unconventional shale oil, possessing the characteristics of type II and Type II/III kerogen type (Oladotun & Olugbenga, 2018). The Anambra basin and the Niger Delta basins also have commercial quantities of shale oil and gas; and the possibilities of finding more viable commercial resources of unconventional petroleum resources are very bright/encouraging, due to the existence of seepages of shale oil in some other basins around the country. Shale oil seepages have also been reported around Lokpanta in southeastern Nigeria with a predominance of gas-prone facies, showing the prospects of finding unconventional petroleum in this and other Nigerian inland sedimentary basins (Onuoha & Chidizie, 2016).

The Challenges of Shale Oil Exploration in Nigeria

The major challenges of shale oil and gas exploration in Nigeria includes:

i) **Slow rate of penetration:** The shale oil and gas are found in the rock formations and as such the rate of penetration through the rock formation is difficult due to increased differential pressure and in-situ stresses, decreased porosity and decreased rate of drill cuttings removal. Properties such as abrasiveness, compressive strength, permeability and swelling clays also affects the rate of penetration, hence high force is required to rotate the drill string/bit during the drilling process. The abrasiveness also influences the rate of bit wear and changes during drilling.

ii) **Well bore stability:** Shales have low strength and permeability, this can result in breakout or caving-in of near-wellbore rocks (well enlargement) and reduction of wellbore size (well tightening) during drilling/completion operations. The drilled wells can also experience swelling, hydration, strength reduction and failure. Well enlargement/ Tightening are usually caused by the strength reduction of near-wellbore rocks

because of the pressure gradient between the drilling mud in the well and the formation pressure in addition to the in-situ stress being greater than the well pressure. Failure is usually caused by plastic or brittle deformation; plastic deformation leads to well reduction, and brittle deformation results in well enlargement: generation and removal of large quantities of broken rock from the well. Well tightening causes reduced drilling rate, stuck pipes which prevents the drill pipe from rotating. While enlargement on the other hand is capable of causing an increase in the quantity of drill cuttings generated and brought to the surface which reduces the quality and serviceability of the drilling mud. There is also the risk of failures as a result of the deflection and bending stress the pipe may experience in the enlarged zone (Okeke & Okogbue, 2011).

Another challenge to the exploration of unconventional resources in Nigeria is the absence of an enabling law and regulatory frame work governing their exploration and subsequent exploration. The Nigerian Government is not abreast with the current trends in the petroleum industry. Another challenge is poor investment climate as a result of security risks; majority of Nigeria's oil is from onshore fields, the Niger Delta region of the country and are more prone to terrorism and sabotage (Onuoha & Chidozie, 2016).

Conclusion

Nigeria is blessed with abundant natural resources including sources of energy; the conventional crude oil and gas, the nonconventional (shale deposits), solar (sunlight), and hydro; but Nigeria has totally depended on conventional oil and gas for its source of energy leaving the other sources unexplored. Most recently there has been an evolution and demand for shale oil in the global oil market especially by the US, and this has led to the fall in the demand for Nigeria's crude oil and consequences such as debts, economy retardation and inflation. Though there are potential drawbacks, these can be addressed through careful planning and responsible development. As the energy industry continues to evolve, shale oil extraction will play an important role in meeting the world's increasing energy demand.

Recommendations:

It is highly recommended that Nigeria should participate in shale oil exploitation to:

- i) diversify the means of energy generation
- ii) reduce the cost of providing energy
- iii) have other sources of energy instead of depending on one source
- iv) legal and institutional framework and effective implementation strategy for the exploration and production of shale oil should be put in place.
- v) Investors should be provided with security and incentives/rewards.
- vi) the Nigerian government to trains her own citizens in the various aspects of exploring, and running the oil industry.

References

- Abas, N., Kalair, A. and Khan, N. (2015). Review of fossil fuels and future energy technologies. *Futures*, 69, 31 - 49.
- Agbaeze, K.E., Udeh, S.N. and Onuka, I.O. (2015). Resolving Nigeria's dependency on oil. The derivation model. *Journal of African Studies and Development*, 7 (1): 1 – 4.
- Biglarbigi, K., Mohan, H., Crawford, P. and Carolus, M. (2007) Potential for oil shale development in the United States. *Society of Petroleum Engineers*, SPE Paper 110590.
- EIA (US Energy Information Administration), 2021).

- Enze, W., Yue, F., Tonglou, G. and Maowen, L. (2022). Oil content and resource quality evaluation methods for lacustrine shale: A review and novel three dimensional quality evaluation mode. *Earth Science Review*. 232: 104134.
- Jiang, Z., Zhang, W., Liang, C., Wang, Y., Liu, H., Chen, X. (2016). Basic characteristics and evaluation of shale oil reservoirs. *Petroleum Research*, 1, 149 - 163.
- Makeen, Y. M., Abdullah, W.H., Ayinla, H.A., Hakimi, M.H., and Sia, S.-G. (2015). Sedimentology, diagenesis and reservoir quality of the upper Abu Gabra Formation sandstones in the Fula Sub-basin, Muglad Basin, Sudan. *Marine and Petroleum Geology*, 77, 1227 - 1242.
- Obasi, S. (2013). Nigeria missing from Global Shale Oil Production. (*Vanguard Newspaper*, June 24, 2013).
- Ofodile, S.E, Boisa, N, Obunwo, C.C and Frank, O.M (2018). Characterisation of Oil Properties from a Niger Delta Crude Ofodile et al., *J Environ Anal Toxicol* 8:(2)1000563.
- Ogidi, A.O., Essien, N.U., Okon, E.E., Nton, M.E. and Jackson, C.A. (2021). Evolution of the shale gas potential of Ekenkpon shale, Calabar Flank, Southeastern Nigeria. Nigerian Association of *Petroleum Explorationists (NAPE) Bulletin*, 30 (1): 55 – 69.
- Okon, A.N. and Olagunju, D.T. (2017) Economic estimation of shale oil development in Nigeria. *Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, 4(9): 397 – 408.
- Osuji, L.C. (2015). The future of petroleum in Nigeria and prospects of shale oil as an alternative energy supplier. *Journal of Chemical Society of Nigeria*. 40: 1 - 4
- PEDIAA (2016) Differences between crude oil and shale oil. [Pediaa.com/difference-between-crude-oil-and-shale-oil](https://www.pediaa.com/difference-between-crude-oil-and-shale-oil).
- Okeke, O.C. and Okogbue, C.O. (2011). Shales: A review of their classifications, properties and importance to the petroleum industry. *Global Journal of Geological Sciences*. 9: 55 – 73.
- Oladotun, A.O. and Olugbenga, A.E. (2018). Potential shale resource plays in southeastern Nigeria. Petroleum system modelling and microfabric perspectives. *Journal of African Earth Sciences* 138: 247 – 257.
- Onuoha, K.M. and Chidozie, I.P.D. (2016). Prospects and Challenges of developing unconventional petroleum resources in the Anambra inland basin of Nigeria. African Energy and Technology Conference. Nairobi, Kenya.
- Tissot, B.P. and Welte, D.H. (1984). Petroleum formation and occurrence. 2nd Edition, Springer-Verlag, Berlin 699 pp.
- Turgut, B. and Yilmaaz, O.A. (2016). The advantages and disadvantages of the production of shale gas production: the case study of Turkey. *Researchgate*. www.researchgate.net.
- Vandenbroucke, M. and Largeau, C. (2007). Kerogen origin, evolution and structure. *Organic Geochemistry*. 38 (5): 719 – 833.
- Wikipedia (2023). History of shale oil industry. Retrived from en.m Wikipedia.org on 24 may, 2023.
- Yue, F., Xianming, X., Enze, W., Jian, S. and Ping, G. (2021). Oil retention in shales: A review of the mechanism, controls assessment. *Frontiers in Earth Science*. 9: 720839.
- Zhou, H., Zeng, S., Xu, G. and Qian, Y. (2018). Modelling and analysis of oil shale refinery process with the indirectly heated moving bed. *Carbon Resources Conversion*, 1 (3): 260 – 265